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Analogue learning in the digital age

Can we use ‘old-fashioned’ active learning methods to educate engineers in the modern world?

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INTRODUCTION

“Digitisation” and “digital transformation” are recent buzz words in both industry as well as academia, where we aim to prepare students for success within their future careers. This digital transformation push within the university setting can be seen in simple actions, such as transitions to digital exams and creating of interactive learning spaces¹; in teaching aspects, such as increased focus on topics related to, for example, Big Data and Building Information Modelling (BIM); and even in research, with calls for proposals specifically related to digital transformation². This then raises the question, should all aspects of the learning process strive towards digitisation, or is there still continued benefit to learning concepts the old-fashioned way?

The course examined in this research, Geometric Design of Roads, is a course within the civil engineering curriculum where the students use geometry and physics theory to design road alignments, also considering economics, environment and aesthetics. This design process is iterative: one has to create different alignments to find one that meets design criteria and achieves an acceptable compromise between often conflicting interests. Professionally, this design process is currently aided by specialised computer software, which allows the engineer to calculate, visualise and compare the impact of several alternatives much faster than if it were to be done as in the pre-computer era: by hand, using paper maps, curve rulers, and elbow grease.

¹ <https://www.ntnu.no/laeringsarealer>

² <https://innsida.ntnu.no/wiki/-/wiki/English/Call+for+project+proposals+++Digital+transformation/>

In the aforementioned course, the principals of road alignment design are taught, in part, through active, project-based learning methods in which the students are presented with a realistic job task of designing a road alignment for a given location. When the term “active learning” is used here, it is grounded in the definition provided by Prince [1], who states that active learning is “any instructional method that engages students in the learning process”, in contrast to the more passive traditional lecture format. The effectiveness of active learning has been documented by Prince [1] and more recently in a meta-analysis [2]. Project-based learning is one type of active learning method that is characterized by (although not exclusively) tasks that are similar to professional issues, is directed toward application of knowledge, and requires both self-direction on the part of the student and cooperation in teams. Project-based learning activities have been indicated to be effective in teaching design methods in engineering education [3] [4].

The two project-based tasks examined in this study are intended to be authentic and emulate the complexity of an actual professional project, although one is performed not with the use of current software, but in the old-fashioned way with paper maps and rulers. Both drawings and computer models are central to the active learning activities in the course at hand, as in most engineering design processes. These are representations, and are used not only to communicate or document results, but also to individually and collaboratively think about the task, and synthesise ideas [5]. Representations can be sketches, prototypes or computer models, but Henderson [6] has pointed out that the flexibility of more informal, analogue sketches during a design process is at risk of getting lost when designing solely with digital tools, which affects the thought processes that rely on it. An education specific issue of representations is that when new technology is brought into the classroom one tends to ask how it can improve learning, but forgets to ask what the analogue representations that are being replaced did for learning in the first place [7].

It has been anecdotally observed that the activity consisting of designing roads by hand helps the students synthesize theoretical concepts at a perhaps higher level than within the similar activity using current design software. It is hypothesized that a large share of the theoretical learning occurred during this old-fashioned project task, despite its distance from current technological practice. We therefore sought to assess whether the old-fashioned design process is still relevant as an active learning project for students to develop their newfound knowledge in the modern world. This was examined during the length of one semester of the course, through surveys aimed at mapping students’ perceived learning as well as actual learning, and a focus group interview after the conclusion of the course.

1 THE COURSE CONTEXT

The course is divided into three phases. The first phase of the course (5 weeks) consists of traditional lectures and individual assignments. In this phase the students are introduced to the theoretical concepts of road design, in addition to considerations of regulations, and social and environmental requirements. Each weekly lecture (3 hours) covers one topic, and the five main topics are accompanied by a relatively short exercise intended to provide repetition and illustrate use of the concepts and mathematical tools provided in the lecture. The exercises are compulsory but ungraded. It should be noted that one lecture topic was presented in a flipped classroom model over the course of the study. This was experimental in nature and discussed briefly in the results.

The second phase of the course (5 weeks) consists of a project-based task, hereafter referred to as the “old-fashioned project”. Students are divided into groups of four or

five, and given a map of a terrain and curve rulers to construct a road alignment. They are to design an alignment (both horizontal and vertical) between two points on the map. The road alignment has to satisfy current national design requirements, be safe and comfortable to drive on, and fit well to the topography. The resulting alignment is to be documented and discussed in a final report.

During the final phase of the course (3 weeks) students are introduced to the road module of a Building Information Modelling (BIM) tool. This software is frequently used professionally and competence in this tool is a sought-after skill in road engineers. Similarly to the old-fashioned project, students work in groups of two or three on a task (hereafter referred to as the “software project”) of designing a road using this tool. Again, the road alignment has to satisfy current national design requirements, be safe and comfortable to drive on, and fit well to the topography. The software project has a second objective to allow students to familiarize themselves with the sophisticated software. The project task culminates with an informal presentation of the road alignment, evaluating both the design and knowledge of the software.

Both the old-fashioned project and the software project are compulsory and graded exercises within the course. *Fig. 1* shows students working with both projects.

Fig. 1. Students working with the old-fashioned project (left) and software project (right)

2 METHODS

Two methods were employed during the study to understand the efficacy of the various learning methods: student surveys and a focus group.

In order to assess how the different phases of the course contributed to learning, six surveys were scheduled throughout the course, see *Table 1* for an overview. As there was a possibility that within different topics, the different learning methods would yield different learning outcomes, the surveys focused on three specific topics: (1) horizontal alignment, (2) vertical alignment and (3) aesthetics. As stated previously, these were lectured over one week each, and topics 1 and 2 had corresponding individual exercises.

The surveys were similar in setup. Students were asked to rate their learning outcome on a five-step likert scale, and also answer two concept questions to objectively measure actual learning from the lecture and assignment combined. This would reveal any discrepancy between self-assessed and actual learning. See *Fig. 2* for an example of a concept question. Two more surveys were distributed after the deadlines of the projects. In these the students were asked to rate their knowledge gain in the three topics (horizontal alignment, vertical alignment, and aesthetic), to find whether students experienced any additional learning during either of the two projects. Selected concept questions covering all three topics were also asked again.

Table 1. Course and questionnaire schedule

Phase	Week	Content	Survey
Lectures and individual assignments	1	Road planning process	
	2	Horizontal curvature (HC)	1 Horizontal curvature - self-assessed learning gain - concept questions
	3	Sight control	
	4	Vertical curvature (VC) (flipped classroom trial)	2 Vertical curvature - self-assessed learning gain - concept questions
	5	Aesthetics (A)	3 Aesthetics - self-assessed learning gain - concept questions
Old-fashioned project	6	Self-directed project work with guidance	
	7		
	8		
	9		
	10		4 Old-fashioned project - self-assessed learning gain in HC, VC, A - evaluation of learning gain from project in HC, VC, A
Software project	11	Self-directed project work with guidance	
	12		
	13		5 Software project - self-assessed learning gain in HC, VC, A - evaluation of learning gain from project in HC, VC, A
	15		6 End survey - effectiveness rating of all learning resources

As the overhøyde increases, the minimum horizontal curve

A Increases
 B Decreases
 C Stays the same

Fig. 2. Example of concept question from the surveys

In the final survey, following the conclusion of in-class activities and project deadlines, the students were asked to rate the effectiveness of each learning resource, such as lecture notes and assignments that had been available to the students throughout the course.

All surveys were anonymous, voluntary, and utilized an online survey platform. The surveys were distributed to a class of approximately 80 students.

The intent of the surveys was to provide an indication of when, and to what degree learning occurred, and would therefore show whether the old-fashioned project in the second phase of the course was successful in improving theoretical understanding. However, the surveys do not provide any insight into why learning was successful in any of the three phases, or give any other understanding of how learning occurred for the students doing the activities. Therefore, the surveys were supplemented by a focus

group interview conducted two months after the final exam of the course. Seven volunteer participants were enlisted. In the focus group, students were asked about their experience in the course in general, and in the old-fashioned project and software project specifically. Emphasis was put on how theoretical understanding was acquired in order to arrive at a finished road alignment in the projects. In addition to evaluating how theoretical concepts were internalised during the phases, the participants were also asked to reflect on whether there were any other outcomes – positive or negative – from the different activities.

The focus group facilitator was not the instructor of the course, but was knowledgeable in the course, having taken it previously. The focus group utilized an interview guide as a base but allowed for flexibility given the participants' engagement and focus. The interview lasted 1 hour and 15 minutes, and was recorded.

3 RESULTS

The following section presents selected results from both the surveys and focus group. The survey response rates varied between 29 and 49%.

3.1 Surveys

The concept questions in the three surveys given during the initial traditional lecture phase resulted in generally high average scores (students answered correctly). Topic (1), horizontal curvature, had the best results compared to the other topics, but the differences were small. The students also considered their learning outcome to be better in horizontal curvature than the other topics. The respondents were least confident about their degree of learning in topic (3) aesthetics, with an average self-assessment of 2.89 on a scale from 1 to 5. The average self-assessment rating for horizontal curvature was 3.34 and for topic (2) vertical curvature it was 3.00.

Fig. 3 shows how students rate their knowledge gain in the different topics during the two active learning projects. The students report to greatly increase their knowledge during the old-fashioned project from what they already knew from lectures. All of the respondents reported to have learned something during the project, as no one gave the lowest score. The results for the same question in the survey regarding the software project were similar, although to a slightly lesser degree. The concept questions in the survey after the old-fashioned project gave scores at approximately the same level as in the surveys during the first phase for all three topics.

Fig. 4 shows how the respondents in the final survey rated the effectiveness of the different learning resources provided throughout the course. The two projects are listed as 'Active learning projects'. Support from teacher, the learning activities and lectures were rated as moderately to very effective, while the video lectures and curriculum literature were rated as less effective.

3.2 Focus group interview

The participants of the focus group expressed generally positive experiences with the course learning methods. One participant said that they "liked having the curriculum presented at the beginning, and then be able to digest it while working on the project for a longer period of time." Another described the relationship between the individual assignments and the project work: "There was a good balance between practicing specific methods in the individual assignments, methods that not necessarily were used by everyone in the group during the project work, and then later work on the larger projects where you got to see the whole picture and understand how all the pieces fit together."

Fig. 3. Added learning from active learning projects

Fig. 4. Effectiveness of learning resources

Although the old-fashioned project was described as cumbersome and at times frustrating, the participants emphasised that if there had been only one software-aided project, this would have yielded less understanding of the underlying theory: “The software does a lot of the work for you, leaving you to try out input values until all the lights are green. It does all the calculations for you, and so you don’t have to think about it as thoroughly.”

However, they also expressed that the software project contributed to understanding of some of the concepts, especially aesthetics: “It’s difficult to visualise the road in the old-fashioned project, it wasn’t until we made the 3D model of a road in the software project that I fully understood how much destruction a road can cause in the terrain. You don’t see that while drawing the line on the flat map.”

The previously mentioned flipped classroom trial used for the vertical curvature topic was also discussed during the focus group. While it was not the main focus of this study, students' reception to the learning method may impact the study results. The participants of the focus group expressed general scepticism towards the flipped classroom method. Some had not seen the videos at home in advance of class and so had skipped the classroom activities because they didn't feel prepared. Others had come to class even though they hadn't seen the videos in advanced, which meant some of the material presented in the videos had to be revisited at the beginning of class – to the dismay of the students who had actually prepared. The students felt that the flipped model required more effort on their behalf, while not adding more value since they already appreciated the traditional lecture model used for the other topics.

4 DISCUSSION

The motivation for this study was to evaluate how the active, project-based learning activities detailed above, with a specific focus on the old-fashioned project, contributed to students' learning of the underlying theoretical concepts in the road alignment design course. The surveys and the focus group interview show that students experienced added learning outcome from the old-fashioned project work. However, as noted in the survey results, the course participants also reported a significant increase in learning within horizontal curvature, vertical curvature and aesthetics during the software project. This is contrary to statements made in the focus group, where participants expressed they had already learned most of the theoretical concepts during the old-fashioned project before encountering more technical challenges in the software project. Therefore it is uncertain whether the students answering the surveys understood that they were to rate increase in knowledge, and not e.g. general understanding. In hindsight, it might have been better to pose these questions in parallel instead of several weeks apart, so that the comparison became clearer. Regardless, the results indicate there is value in both old-fashioned project work, as well as the software project.

Since the respondents scored quite well during the first concept tests in surveys one to three (testing knowledge after traditional lectures and individual exercises), there was not much room for improvement on these questions in the survey following the old-fashioned project and software project, and therefore it was not a surprise that the results were similar on these surveys. One possible reason might be that the concept questions, in form, were much like the questions posed on the individual exercises during phase one. It is also noted that students seemed to have gained understanding on vertical curvature even though the flipped classroom model used to teach this topic received mixed feedback.

Despite inconclusive results from the concept questions on objective knowledge gain during the old-fashioned project, the testimonies from the focus group interview support the hypothesis that the old-fashioned project helps in synthesising concepts. One could imagine that having to learn a design method that no future employer utilizes directly, and that is inarguably workload-heavy, repetitive and at times frustrating compared to modern standards, would bring down students' motivation in the course, but that does not seem to be the case. Overall students appear to understand why the old-fashioned method is taught and even enjoy the process of drawing and plotting on large paper maps, gaining also from sketching by hand as both a way of sorting and synthesising ideas, as well as providing a common ground for students and teachers to discuss ideas and collaborate. This is in addition to the other benefits associated with problem-based learning. Additionally, it is important to note that while the method employed in the old-fashioned activity is no longer utilized in practice, it is not fully

outdated as the digital tools provide an automatization of the old-fashioned methods. Thus understanding the methodology behind the software helps students understand its output.

5 CONCLUSION

In an age of digital transformation, this research considers whether “old-fashioned” methodologies are still relevant within the learning process. A series of surveys and a focus group within an ongoing course were used to better understand the efficacy of the various learning methods, both analog and digital. While there is a risk of bias in the results, due to that the more eager, motivated students might be more willing to take part in surveys and a focus group than their counterparts, the results of this study indicate that old-fashioned methodologies can still be utilized as an effective and enjoyable learning activity in today’s modern and increasingly digital world.

REFERENCES

- [1] Prince, M. (2004), Does Active Learning Work? A Review of the Research, *Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 93, No. 3, pp. 223-231.
- [2] Freeman, S., Eddy S.L., McDonough M., Smith M.K., Okoroafor N., Jordt H. and Wenderoth M.P. (2014), Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, Vol. 111, No. 23, pp. 8410-8415.
- [3] Mills, J.E. and Treagust D.F. (2003), Engineering education – is problem-based or project-based learning the answer?, *Australasian Journal of Engineering Education*, online publication 2003-04, previously published at: www.aeee.com.au/journal/2003/mills_treagust03.pdf.
- [4] Dym, C.L., Agogino, A.M., Eris O., Frey D.D. and Leifer L.J. (2005), Engineering Design Thinking, Teaching and Learning, *Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 94, No. 1, pp. 103-120.
- [5] Juhl, J. and Lindegaard, H. (2013), Representations and Visual Synthesis in Engineering Design, *Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 102, No. 1, pp. 20-50.
- [6] Henderson, K. (1998), The Role of Material Objects in the Design Process: A Comparison of Two Design Cultures and How They Contend with Automation. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, Vol. 23, No. 2, pp. 139-174.
- [7] Sørensen, E. (2009). *The Materiality of Learning: Technology and Knowledge in Educational Practice*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, pp. 190-191.